

"High canopy cover of invasive *Acer negundo* L. affects ground vegetation taxonomic richness"

ANOVA and ANCOVA results description, discussed in the manuscript

Canopy cover

Inter-habitat comparison

Canopy cover; inter-habitat comparison; ANOVA with fixed and random effects; $dF_{\text{error}} = 54$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Canopy cover	Plot type (fixed effects)	1	11.09	0.0016
	Year (fixed effects)	2	3.55	0.0356
	Plot type × year (fixed effects)	2	0.33	0.7186
	Site (random effect)	12	5.57	<0.0001

Intra-habitat comparison

Canopy cover; intra-habitat comparison; one-way ANOVA; $dF_{\text{error}} = 797$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Canopy cover	Plot type (fixed effects)	2	4.21	0.0151

Canopy cover; intra-habitat comparison; ANOVA with fixed (plot type) and random effect (block 5×5); $dF_{\text{error}} = 558$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Canopy cover	Plot type (fixed effects)	2	9.98	<0.0001
	Block 5×5 (random effect)	239	1.19	0.0516

Canopy cover; intra-habitat comparison; ANOVA with fixed (plot type) and random effect (block 10×10); $dF_{\text{error}} = 692$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Canopy cover	Plot type (fixed effects)	2	4.63	0.0100
	Block 10×10 (random effect)	105	1.66	0.0001

Canopy cover; intra-habitat comparison; ANOVA with fixed (plot type) and random effect (block 20×20); $dF_{\text{error}} = 766$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Canopy cover	Plot type (fixed effects)	2	6.49	0.0016
	Block 20×20 (random effect)	31	1.41	0.0697

Richness of ground cover

Inter-habitat comparison

Richness of ground cover; inter-habitat comparison; ANOVA with fixed and random effects; $dF_{\text{error}} = 54$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Richness of ground cover	Plot type (fixed effects)	1	63.69	<0.0001
	Year (fixed effects)	2	0.30	0.7433
	Plot type × year (fixed effects)	2	1.22	0.3031
	Site (random effect)	12	10.44	<0.0001

Intra-habitat comparison

Richness of ground cover; intra-habitat comparison; one-way ANOVA; $dF_{\text{error}} = 797$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Richness of ground cover	Plot type (fixed effects)	2	28.58	<0.0001

Richness of ground cover; intra-habitat comparison; ANOVA with fixed (plot type) and random effect (block 5×5); $dF_{\text{error}} = 558$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Richness of ground cover	Plot type (fixed effects)	2	10.87	<0.0001
	Block 5×5 (random effect)	239	1.30	0.0065

Richness of ground cover; intra-habitat comparison; ANOVA with fixed (plot type) and random effect (block 10×10); $dF_{\text{error}} = 692$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Richness of ground cover	Plot type (fixed effects)	2	14.55	<0.0001
	Block 10×10 (random effect)	105	1.69	<0.0001

Richness of ground cover; intra-habitat comparison; ANOVA with fixed (plot type) and random effect (block 20×20); $dF_{\text{error}} = 766$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Richness of ground cover	Plot type (fixed effects)	2	25.75	<0.0001
	Block 10×10 (random effect)	31	1.93	0.0020

Relationship between canopy cover and species richness of ground cover

Inter-habitat comparison

Richness of ground cover; inter-habitat comparison; ANCOVA with fixed effects; $dF_{\text{error}} = 60$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Richness of ground cover	Plot type	1	13.61	0.0005
	Year	2	0.54	0.5866
	Canopy cover	1	6.02	0.0170
	Plot type × year	2	0.54	0.5866
	Plot type × canopy cover	1	<0.01	0.9949
	Year × canopy cover	2	0.04	0.9574
	Plot type × year × canopy cover	2	0.24	0.7898

Intra-habitat comparison

Richness of ground cover; intra-habitat comparison; ANCOVA with fixed effects; $dF_{\text{error}} = 794$

Dependent variable	Predictors (factors)	<i>dF</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
Richness of ground cover	Plot type	2	25.73	<0.0001
	Canopy cover	1	12.43	0.0004
	Plot type × canopy cover	1	1.69	0.1855